

Seasonal Prediction of Rainfall Variability in the West African Sudan-Sahel

Manuel Rauch^{1, 2}, Jan Bliefernicht¹, Windmanagda Sawadogo¹, Souleymane SY¹, Moussa Waongo³, Harald Kunstmann^{2*}

¹University of Augsburg, Germany, ²Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany, ³Agrhymet Regional Centre, Niger

Submitted to Journal:
Frontiers in Water

Specialty Section:
Water and Hydrocomplexity

Article type:
Original Research Article

Manuscript ID:
1523898

Received on:
15 Nov 2024

Journal website link:
www.frontiersin.org

Scope Statement

This manuscript presents an evaluation of seasonal rainfall prediction models for the Sudan-Sahel region, an area where rainfall variability poses significant risks to agriculture and water management. Through the assessment of traditional models alongside a novel atmospheric circulation-based model, this study provides a framework for more accurate and reliable seasonal rainfall forecasting in the West African region.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest

Credit Author Statement

Harald Kunstmann: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Jan Bliefernicht: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Manuel Rauch: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Moussa Waongo: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Souleymane SY: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Windmanagda Sawadogo: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

Keywords

Seasonal rainfall prediction, rainfall variability, Sudan-Sahel region, West Africa, Forecast verification methods

Abstract

Word count: 189

The Sudan-Sahel region in West Africa is highly vulnerable to rainfall variability, which poses significant challenges to agriculture and water resource management. This study provides an assessment of seasonal rainfall prediction models in the region, focusing on the West African Regional Climate Outlook Forum (WARCOF, 1998(WARCOF, -2023)), the latest generation of the seasonal forecasting system from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF SEAS5, 1981-2023), and a novel atmospheric circulation-pattern-based logistic regression model. The circulation-pattern-based model, which integrates key atmospheric dynamics like near-surface wind anomalies, outperforms both WAR-COF and SEAS5 in predicting interannual rainfall variability. While WARCOF and SEAS5 demonstrate some predictive skill, both models exhibit biases: WARCOF has a dry bias, and SEAS5 displays both dry and wet biases. The circulation-pattern-based model, despite a slight wet bias, delivers more accurate categorical predictions and offers greater reliability. An economic value analysis reveals that the circulation-pattern-based model provides a broader range of positive economic outcomes, making it more suitable for decision-making across various cost-loss scenarios. By introducing this novel model and evaluating traditional forecasting techniques, this study lays the groundwork for more accurate and reliable seasonal rainfall predictions.

Funding information

The author(s) declare financial support was received for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. This study is part of the FURIFLOOD (Current and future risks of urban and rural flooding in West Africa) project, which was funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research in Germany (grant number: 01LG2086D).

Funding statement

The author(s) declare that financial support was received for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Ethics statements

Studies involving animal subjects

Generated Statement: No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

Studies involving human subjects

Generated Statement: No human studies are presented in the manuscript.

Inclusion of identifiable human data

Generated Statement: No potentially identifiable images or data are presented in this study.

In review

Data availability statement

Generated Statement: The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/supplementary material, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author/s.

Generative AI disclosure

The author(s) verify and take full responsibility for the use of generative AI in the preparation of this manuscript. Generative AI was used

Chat-GPT was used for grammar and spell checking.

In review

Seasonal Prediction of Rainfall Variability in the West African Sudan-Sahel

Manuel Rauch^{1,2}, Jan Bliefernicht¹, Windmanagda Sawadogo¹, Souleymane Sy¹,
Moussa Waongo³, and Harald Kunstmann^{*1,2}

¹Institute of Geography, University of Augsburg, Augsburg, Germany

²Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research (IMK-IFU), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology,
Campus Alpin, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, Germany

³Department of Information and Research, Regional Center AGRHYMET, Niamey, Niger

Abstract

The Sudan-Sahel region in West Africa is highly vulnerable to rainfall variability, which poses significant challenges to agriculture and water resource management. This study provides an assessment of seasonal rainfall prediction models in the region, focusing on the West African Regional Climate Outlook Forum (WARCOF, 1998–2023), the latest generation of the seasonal forecasting system from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF SEAS5, 1981–2023), and a novel atmospheric circulation-pattern-based logistic regression model (1981–2023). The circulation-pattern-based model, which integrates key atmospheric dynamics like near-surface wind anomalies, outperforms both WARCOF and SEAS5 in predicting interannual rainfall variability. While WARCOF and SEAS5 demonstrate some predictive skill, both models exhibit biases: WARCOF has a dry bias, and SEAS5 displays both dry and wet biases. The circulation-pattern-based model, despite a slight wet bias, delivers more accurate categorical predictions and offers greater reliability. An economic value analysis reveals that the circulation-pattern-based model provides a broader range of positive economic outcomes, making it more suitable for decision-making across various cost-loss scenarios. By introducing this novel model and evaluating traditional forecasting techniques, this study lays the groundwork for more accurate and reliable seasonal rainfall predictions.

Keywords: seasonal rainfall prediction, rainfall variability, Sudan-Sahel region, West Africa

*Corresponding author: harald.kunstmann@kit.edu

28 1 Introduction

29 The Sudan-Sahel region has experienced significant interannual variability in seasonal rainfall over recent
30 decades (Nouaceur and Murarescu, 2020; Rauch et al., 2024), presenting a major challenge due to the
31 high dependence on rain-fed agriculture and pastoralism (Zampaligré et al., 2014; Coly et al., 2024).
32 Livelihoods are highly vulnerable to changes in seasonal rainfall patterns (Mertz et al., 2012). Accu-
33 rate seasonal rainfall forecasts are therefore critical for reducing vulnerability and enhancing resilience
34 in sectors such as agriculture and water resource management (Yengoh, 2012). Inaccurate or limited
35 predictions of droughts, for instance, can have far-reaching effects on food security, economic stability,
36 and water availability (Wilhite et al., 2007; Hao et al., 2018). Thus, improving seasonal rainfall predic-
37 tions would enable stakeholders to better prepare for such events, mitigating their adverse effects and
38 enhancing disaster preparedness (Portele et al., 2021).

39 In many parts of the world, seasonal predictions are generated by Regional Climate Outlook Forums
40 (RCOFs), which bring together climate experts from national, regional, and international institutions
41 (Semazzi, 2011). These forums aim to develop and disseminate seasonal climate outlooks, typically
42 once or multiple times a year, tailored to specific geographic regions. The forum currently serving the
43 Sudan-Sahel region in West Africa is known as *Prévisions Climatiques Saisonnières en Afrique Soudano-*
44 *Sahélienne* (PRESASS). This forum is organized by the *African Centre of Meteorological Application for*
45 *Development* (ACMAD) and the *Centre Regional de Formation et d'Application en Agrométéorologie et*
46 *Hydrologie Opérationnelle* (AGRYMET), which regularly convene in April or May to produce forecasts for
47 the rainy season (Bliefernicht et al., 2019). These forecasts focus on June, July, August or July, August,
48 September (JAS) periods and are disseminated to stakeholders in the form of maps and advisory docu-
49 ments, which serve as critical tools for decision-making across various sectors. The forecasting process
50 categorizes seasonal rainfall into terciles (below-average, near-average, and above-average), where each
51 tercile represents one-third of the long-term climatological data (typically 1981–2010). These categories
52 are communicated through maps that indicate the likelihood of each category occurring across different
53 regions. This approach helps simplify complex climate data into actionable insights for local decision-
54 makers (Fig. 1). For a more detailed discussion of this forecasting methodology, see Bliefernicht et al.
55 (2019) and Pirret et al. (2020).

56 Mason and Chidzambwa (2008) conducted the first assessment of seasonal precipitation forecasts pro-
57 duced by the West African RCOF (WARCOF) for the period 1998 to 2007, identifying both positive skill
58 in predicting below-normal and above-normal precipitation, as well as several limitations, particularly a
59 lack of sharpness. Extending this analysis to 2013, Bliefernicht et al. (2019) confirmed these findings but
60 also highlighted issues such as overforecasting near-normal conditions, which were attributed to forecast-
61 ers' risk aversion. Similarly, Pirret et al. (2020) observed a bias in the WARCOF forecasts (1998–2017)
62 toward underestimating probabilities for the below-normal category, linked to similar hedging behaviors
63 identified in previous studies. Houngnibo et al. (2023) identified the temporal aggregation of forecasts
64 as a significant limitation and proposed a temporal disaggregation method to address this issue. These
65 forecasting limitations, including biases and temporal aggregation, hinder optimal decision-making, par-
66 ticularly in agriculture and water resource management, where accurate forecasts are critical. Therefore,
67 further evaluation and development of more advanced forecasting methods within the WARCOF process
68 are essential.

69 Operational seasonal forecasting models that support the WARCOF are relatively rare in West Africa.
70 Many downscaling studies have primarily focused on developing and evaluating dynamical approaches
71 (e.g., Siegmund et al. 2015; Klein et al. 2015; Paeth et al. 2017), which are computationally expensive, or
72 providing regional climate projections (e.g., Lorenz et al. 2018; Siabi et al. 2021; Polasky et al. 2024). In
73 contrast, statistical downscaling frameworks have shown significant promise, offering a more accessible
74 and efficient alternative. For example, Ndiaye et al. (2011) used a linear least squares regression based

**SEASONAL PRECIPITATION FORECAST
FOR SUDANO-SAHELIAN REGION OF AFRICA
VALID FOR JULY-AUGUST-SEPTEMBER 2022
ISSUED ON APRIL 25, 2022**

Figure 1: An example of the West African Regional Climate Outlook Forum rainfall outlook for JAS 2022 (ACMAD, 2022).

75 on the time series of the first empirical orthogonal function from tropical Atlantic low-level winds as the
76 predictor and the Sahel rainfall index as the predictand for seasonal rainfall forecasting. Manzanas (2017)
77 applied the analog method for downscaling temperature and rainfall in Senegal, while Rauch et al. (2019)
78 employed a simple bias correction (quantile-quantile mapping) to refine rainfall data for forecasting the
79 onset of the rainy season. A further overview and examples of downscaling techniques for rainfall in West
80 Africa is given in Paeth et al. (2011). Moreover, the reconstruction based on atmospheric circulation
81 patterns (CPs) in combination with a logistic regression model of the interannual rainfall variability in
82 West Africa as detailed in Rauch et al. (2024) shows promise in improving the predictive skill of seasonal
83 rainfall forecasts.

84 To address these challenges, the present study focuses on enhancing seasonal rainfall predictions
85 by applying the statistical downscaling method developed by Rauch et al. (2024). This method builds
86 on integrating reliable atmospheric processes, aiming to improve reliability and reduce forecast errors.
87 Additionally, a comprehensive long-term evaluation of WARCOF's regional forecasts (1998–2023) will
88 be presented, comparing their performance against the global seasonal forecast system (SEAS5 from
89 ECMWF, Johnson et al. 2019) and the method of Rauch et al. (2024) for the period of 1981 to 2023.
90 Through the use of advanced forecast verification tools, such as the ranked probability skill score (e.g.,
91 Weigel et al. 2007), the multi-category reliability diagram (Hamill, 1997), and an economic value frame-
92 work (e.g., Bliefernicht et al. 2019), this study will offer deeper insights into the accuracy and practical
93 value of seasonal rainfall predictions. By applying these evaluation tools, we aim to provide a clearer un-
94 derstanding of the strengths and limitations of both regional and global forecasting systems, ultimately
95 contributing to more reliable seasonal forecasts for decision-makers in West Africa.

96 2 Target Region

97 For this evaluation, we focus on the Sudan-Sahel region (5.5°W 11°N to 2.4°E 13.5°N , Fig. 2) as the
98 target area, following a similar domain as Bliefernicht et al. (2019). This region was chosen due to its
99 relatively high density of in-situ rainfall stations (see Fig. 3 in Bliefernicht et al. 2019), which likely
100 improves the reliability of the remote sensing precipitation products. This region experiences a single,
101 short rainy season spanning from June to September with a peak in August (Bliefernicht et al., 2022;
102 Rauch et al., 2024).

Figure 2: The dashed domain indicates the predictor domain (30°W 5°S to 40°E 40°N), the smaller domain (solid) highlights the target area (5.5°W 11°N to 2.4°E 13.5°N).

103 3 Material and Methods

104 This section outlines the materials and methods used for the preprocessing, development, and evaluation
105 of the selected seasonal rainfall prediction models for the Sudan-Sahel region. An overview of the workflow
106 is provided in Fig. 3.

107 3.1 CHIRPS

108 Due to the lack of access to recent observational data and the goal of developing an operational framework,
109 we use the Climate Hazards Group Infrared Precipitation with Stations (CHIRPS) product (Funk et al.,
110 2015). CHIRPS combines satellite rainfall estimates with gauge and station data corrections, providing
111 a relatively reliable dataset that balances the wide coverage of satellite data with the accuracy of ground-
112 based measurements. This product offers rainfall data on a 0.05° grid, covering the period from 1981
113 to the present. Furthermore, CHIRPS is selected for its proven performance, long-term availability, and

Figure 3: Workflow for seasonal rainfall prediction model evaluation in the Sudan-Sahel region. The process involves three prediction models: WARCOF (West African Regional Climate Outlook Forum), SEAS5 TP (‘raw’ total precipitation output from SEAS5), and CP-based logistic regression (Rauch et al., 2024). Each model is validated against observed CHIRPS (Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Stations) data using the ranked probability skill score, multicategory reliability diagram, and economic value.

114 frequent use in West Africa for studies on rainfall variability and its impacts (Dembélé and Zwart, 2016;
115 Rauch et al., 2019; Pirret et al., 2020; Kouakou et al., 2023).

116 We select all grid points within the target area of Fig. 2, average them spatially to extract a single
117 daily time series, and then aggregate this to standardized annual JAS sums (denoted hereafter as R_A).
118 R_A is then discretized into ordinal classes using two quantile thresholds (q_1 and q_2), where q_1 represents
119 the first and q_2 the second tercile. This classification results in three categories: $R_A \leq q_1$ (Class 1,
120 below-average condition), $q_1 < R_A < q_2$ (Class 2, near-average condition), and $R_A \geq q_2$ (Class 3, above-
121 average condition). These categorizations serve as the target variables in a multi-class logistic regression
122 model (similar to Rauch et al. 2024), ensuring consistency with the outputs of the WARCOF.

123 As illustrated in Fig. 4, the standardized JAS annual rainfall amounts from 1981 to 2023 capture
124 the severe droughts of the 1980s, followed by a recovery in rainfall extending into the early 2020s (Hagos
125 and Cook, 2008; Descroix et al., 2018). This figure not only highlights these climatic trends but also
126 delineates the target evaluation categories used in our analysis.

127 3.2 West African Regional Climate Outlook Forum

128 WARCOF provides seasonal rainfall forecasts tailored for the main rainy season (JAS). The forecasts
129 use tercile-based probabilities to categorize rainfall as below-average, near-average, or above-average
130 (Fig. 1). We use the WARCOF forecast maps from 1998–2017 archived by Pirret et al. (2020) and
131 manually archived maps from 2018 to 2024 (see Fig. S1 - Fig. S7 in the supplementary materials). For
132 each year, we digitized these tercile-based probabilities to create a consistent benchmark dataset for
133 model comparison. This dataset represents the initial standard against which the predictive skill is
134 evaluated.

135 3.3 Seasonal Prediction System from ECMWF

136 The fifth version of ECMWF’s seasonal prediction system (SEAS5) is based on a medium-range atmo-
137 spheric model integrated with ocean, sea ice, land, and wave models (Johnson et al., 2019). SEAS5,
138 operational since November 2017, generates a 51-member ensemble, with hindcasts available from 1981
139 to 2016, consisting of 25 ensemble members initialized on the first of each month. The model data can
140 be downloaded from the Climate Data Store of the Copernicus Climate Change Service.

Figure 4: The standardized interannual rainfall variability for the target region ($\bar{x} = 552.38$ mm, $\sigma = 78.01$ mm) and the period from 1981 to 2023 based on CHIRPS. The solid black line indicates the actual values of standardized annual rainfall sums (JAS). The two dashed lines mark the first and second tercile, dividing the data into three categories: below-average (yellow circle, below the first dashed line), near-average (red square, between the two dashed lines), and above-average (blue diamond, above the second dashed line).

141 As a second benchmark, we use the total precipitation (TP) variable from the forecast system initial-
 142 ized from 1 May. We select all available grid points within the target domain (Fig. 2) to obtain an areal
 143 average of the JAS rainfall sums. This average is then categorized into ordinal classes: below-average,
 144 near-average, and above-average conditions, similar to the CHIRPS preprocessing (Section 3.1) but us-
 145 ing mean and standard deviation of the system itself. However, each ensemble member is categorized
 146 individually to create probabilities for each tercile-based category. The results can be found in Tab. S2.

147 3.4 The CP-based Logistic Regression Model

148 The CP-based logistic regression model employed here closely aligns with that outlined in Rauch et al.
 149 (2024) for reconstructing interannual rainfall anomalies in West Africa. The pre-selection of predictor
 150 variables (Tab. 1) in this study is based on existing literature, aligning with the studies by Moron et al.
 151 (2008); Guèye et al. (2011, 2012); Bliefernicht et al. (2022). To capture dominant regional-scale features
 152 of the West African Monsoon we use a domain spanning from 30°W to 40°E and 5°S to 40°N (see Fig.
 153 2). This domain covers most regions in Africa north of the equator, consistent with the domain size used
 154 by Bliefernicht et al. (2022). To maintain consistency with WARCof, the forecast runs are initialized
 155 from 1 May from ECMWF SEAS5, and the JAS period is selected. For data preparation, standardized
 156 daily anomalies, denoted as $z(i, t, e)$, were derived from the predictor data $x(i, t, e)$ according to:

$$z(i, t, e) = \frac{x(i, t, e) - \bar{x}(i)}{s(i)} \quad (1)$$

157 In this equation, $i = 1, \dots, L$ represents the grid points, $t = 1, \dots, T$ denotes the time steps in days,
158 $e = 1, \dots, E$ indicates the ensemble members, $\bar{x}(i)$ signifies the long-term mean over time and all ensemble
159 members, and $s(i)$ indicates the standard deviation of the time series over time and all ensemble
160 members. This standardized unfiltered daily anomalies are then used to generate daily CPs with cluster
161 counts ranging from 5 to 15 using k-means, and the respective clusters' annual occurrence frequencies are
162 computed for each ensemble individually. These frequencies serve as predictor variables in a multi-class
163 logistic regression model. The predictants in this regression are the classes: below-average, near-average,
164 and above-average conditions (as described in Section 3.1 and shown in Fig. 4). The logistic regres-
165 sion model predicts the category of each rainfall condition for every ensemble, generating probabilistic
166 forecasts similar to those used in WARCOF by assigning probabilities to each tercile-based category.
167 Methodological details about the different components (e.g., k-means or logistic regression) and the
168 general workflow can be found in Rauch et al. (2024).

Table 1: Atmospheric variables from SEAS5, ECMWF: Listing of abbreviations, associated atmospheric pressures, units, and input variables for computation. The designation 'all levels' includes atmospheric pressures at 200hPa, 700hPa, 850hPa, 925hPa.

Name	Abbreviation	Levels	Units	Input
Pressure-level variables				
U-component of wind	U	all levels	m s^{-1}	-
V-component of wind	V	all levels	m s^{-1}	-
Wind direction	WD	all levels	degrees	U, V
Wind speed	WS	all levels	m s^{-1}	U, V
Single-level variables				
10 metre U wind component	10U	-	m s^{-1}	-
10 metre V wind component	10V	-	m s^{-1}	-
Mean sea level pressure	MSLP	-	Pa	-

169 3.5 Validation and Performance Measures

170 The models are trained on the SEAS5 hindcast period (1981 to 2016) and validated using the operational
171 forecast period (2017 to 2023). The *RPS* is calculated separately for the training (t) and validation (v)
172 periods using this split-sampling approach, with further analysis performed using multicategory reliability
173 diagrams, and the economic value and comparisons made to WARCOF and the raw TP output from
174 SEAS5. The evaluation measures are further explained in the subsequent sections.

175 Ranked Probability Skill Score

176 To evaluate the performance of our proposed model, one key metric is the Ranked Probability Score
177 (RPS), which is widely used for probabilistic forecast verification (Kumar et al., 2001; Christensen
178 et al., 2015). The RPS evaluates the accuracy of probabilistic predictions by measuring the cumulative
179 squared differences between the predicted and actual cumulative probabilities across all categories, as
180 implemented by Wilks (2006). The formula for the RPS is given by:

$$\text{RPS} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K (F_{i,k} - O_{i,k})^2 \quad (2)$$

181 where N is the total number of forecasts, K is the number of cumulative categories (e.g., below,
182 near-average, above), $F_{i,k}$ represents the cumulative forecast probability for the i -th event up to and

183 including category k , and $O_{i,k}$ represents the cumulative observed outcome for the i -th event up to and
 184 including category k (1 if the event is in or below category k ; 0 otherwise). A lower RPS indicates better
 185 forecast accuracy, reflecting a closer alignment between predicted probabilities and observed events.

186 To further assess the forecast skill, we calculate the Ranked Probability Skill Score (RPSS), which
 187 measures the performance of our forecasts relative to reference forecasts. The RPSS is computed as
 188 follows:

$$\text{RPSS} = 1 - \frac{\text{RPS}}{\text{RPS}_{\text{ref}}} \quad (3)$$

189 where RPS_{ref} is the RPS of the reference forecast. An RPSS value greater than 0 indicates that the
 190 model outperforms the reference forecast, while a value of 1 indicates a perfect forecast.

191 In this study, we first calculate the RPS for two types of reference forecasts: a persistence forecast,
 192 which assumes that decadal variability strongly influences interannual rainfall variability, and a uniform
 193 distribution forecast, which assigns equal probabilities to each category (0.33, 0.33, 0.33) for each year.
 194 Given that the uniform distribution forecast has a lower RPS value (0.45 compared to 0.93 for the
 195 persistence forecast), indicating better baseline performance, we use it as the reference forecast for
 196 calculating the skill score.

197 While the RPSS provides a single metric of improvement over a reference forecast, additional diag-
 198 nostic tools are required to understand the nature of the forecast errors. In the literature, reliability
 199 diagrams are often used to assess quality for seasonal forecast products to determine conditional biases
 200 in the forecast product (Mason and Chidzambwa, 2008; Bliefernicht et al., 2019; Pirret et al., 2020).

201 Multicategory Reliability Diagram

202 In this chapter, we extend the traditional reliability diagram to evaluate probabilistic forecasts using the
 203 Multicategory Reliability Diagram (MCRD; Hamill 1997). This approach is particularly well-suited for
 204 multicategory forecasts and has been chosen for the following reasons: a conventional reliability diagram
 205 is typically applied to binary events (e.g., rain or no rain). However, seasonal rainfall forecasting often
 206 involves multiple categories. For this type of multicategory forecast, three separate diagrams would
 207 be needed to capture each class. If we focus solely on one specific class, the sample size may be too
 208 small to generate meaningful insights (potentially $N/3$ due to the tercile-based approach). Furthermore,
 209 WARCOF has already been extensively evaluated using traditional methods like reliability diagrams or
 210 receiver operating characteristics (Mason and Chidzambwa, 2008; Bliefernicht et al., 2019; Pirret et al.,
 211 2020). For the purpose of thoroughness, the traditional reliability diagrams have also been included in
 212 the supplementary material (Fig. S8 to Fig. S10).

213 The following explanations are strongly based on Hamill (1997) adapted to the tercile-based seasonal
 214 forecasting process. For each forecast season, the forecaster provides a probability vector predicting the
 215 likelihood that the seasonal rainfall will fall into one of three categories: below-average, near-average, or
 216 above-average rainfall. Let $y_i = [y_{i1}, y_{i2}, y_{i3}]$ represent the forecasted probabilities for year i . For exam-
 217 ple, a forecast for a given year might look like $y_i = [0.4, 0.4, 0.2]$, indicating a 40% probability of below-
 218 average rainfall, a 40% probability of near-average rainfall, and a 20% probability of above-average rain-
 219 fall. To perform reliability analysis with a MCRD, we discretize the forecast probabilities into quantiles.
 220 Specifically, we divide the forecast probability space into preset quantiles: $q \in \{0.10, 0.20, 0.30, \dots, 0.90\}$.
 221 For each forecast y_i , the probability vector is transformed into a category vector z_i , which assigns forecast
 222 categories to each quantile. For example, for the forecast $y_i = [0.4, 0.4, 0.2]$, the corresponding category
 223 vector would be $z_i = [1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 3]$.

224 The calibration (or reliability) at a given quantile q , denoted as C_q , is defined as the probability that
 225 the observed rainfall category o_i is less than the forecast category z_i^q . This metric allows us to quantify
 226 how well the forecasted categories align with the actual observations across different quantiles. Formally,

227 the calibration for a given quantile q is computed by averaging over all N forecast years as follows:

$$C_q = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N P(o_i < z_i^q), \quad (4)$$

228 For any given year, one of three calibration scenarios will occur:

- 229 1. Observed category is less than the forecast category ($o_i < z_i^q$): The observed category is lower
230 than the forecast category, so $P(o_i < z_i^q) = 1$.
- 231 2. Observed category equals the forecast category ($o_i = z_i^q$): In this case, we interpolate between
232 the minimum and maximum quantiles where the forecast and observed categories match. The
233 calibration is determined using the following formula:

$$P(o_i < z_i^q) = \frac{q - q_{\min}}{q_{\max} - q_{\min}}, \quad (5)$$

234 where q_{\min} and q_{\max} are the lowest and highest quantiles where $o_i = z_i^q$.

- 235 3. Observed category is greater than the forecast category ($o_i > z_i^q$): The observed category exceeds
236 the forecast category, so $P(o_i < z_i^q) = 0$.

237 For perfect calibration, C_q should equal the quantile q , meaning that, for example, 25% of obser-
238 vations should fall below the 25th percentile of the forecast distribution. The MCRD is generated by
239 plotting C_q against q , with an uncertainty range representing the 95% confidence interval derived from
240 bootstrap resampling, repeated 1000 times.

241 In addition to the calibration plot, the MCRD includes a checkerboard plot that visualizes the
242 mean absolute category error across quantiles. This helps identify systematic biases or inconsistencies in
243 forecast performance. The checkerboard plot complements the calibration diagram by revealing sharpness
244 and skill across the full range of potential outcomes. For instance, significant deviations between forecast
245 and observed categories at certain quantiles could indicate overconfidence or underprediction in the
246 probabilistic forecasts.

247 Economic Value

248 Besides to forecast skill and quality, it is crucial to address the economic value of a forecast. Consider
249 a decision maker who is concerned about a specific weather event, such as the forecast of rainfall falling
250 into one of the defined tercile categories. For instance, the event A might be defined as "above-average"
251 or "below-average" categories in a seasonal forecast. These forecasts are particularly significant for
252 various sectors, where the amount of rainfall can have substantial economic and safety implications. If
253 this unfavorable weather event occurs and no preventative measures are taken, the decision maker is
254 expected to incur a loss L . The forecast is valuable only if it enables the decision maker to take action
255 to reduce or avoid the potential loss. In this simplified scenario, the decision maker has two options:
256 either continue with normal activities or take protective measures to mitigate the loss. Implementing
257 such measures would incur an additional cost C beyond the usual expenses.

258 A deterministic binary forecasting system provides a straightforward yes/no prediction regarding the
259 occurrence of a specific weather event A . The decision maker opts to take protective measures if the
260 forecast indicates that event A will occur and takes no action if the forecast suggests otherwise. The
261 usefulness of such forecasts for a series of past events can be evaluated by analyzing a contingency table
262 compiled from those previous events (see Richardson 2000; Wilks 2001; Richardson 2011; Bliefert
263 et al. 2019; Portele et al. 2021 for further explanation and examples).

264 To compute the economic value V of the forecast, we first established the cost-loss ratio $\alpha = C/L$,
265 which represents the cost of taking preventive action divided by the potential loss incurred if the event

266 occurs without any action. This ratio is critical as it quantifies the decision-maker’s trade-off between
 267 the cost of action and the potential loss, influencing whether protective measures should be taken based
 268 on the forecast.

269 In probabilistic forecasts, for each probability threshold p_t , the hit rate H and false alarm rate F
 270 can be derived from a contingency table, reflecting the system’s ability to correctly predict events. Here,
 271 a represents the number of correct predictions of the event occurring, b the false alarms, c the missed
 272 events, and d the correct predictions of the event not occurring. The total number of events observed,
 273 n , is $n = a + b + c + d$ (Wilks, 2006).

274 The economic value V was then calculated using the following formula:

$$V = \frac{\min(\alpha, s) - F \cdot (1 - s) \cdot \alpha + H \cdot s \cdot (1 - \alpha) - s}{\min(\alpha, s) - s \cdot \alpha} \quad (6)$$

275 where $s = \frac{a+c}{n}$ represents the baseline probability (Richardson, 2011). The numerator reflects the
 276 difference between the benefits of the forecast (correct predictions adjusted for the cost-loss ratio) and
 277 the baseline probability, while the denominator normalizes this value by the baseline scenario without
 278 the forecast.

279 The value score ranges from $-\infty$ to 1, where a score of 1 indicates perfect forecast performance and
 280 a score of 0 represents no added value over climatology. Negative values suggest that the forecast system
 281 is less effective than the climatological baseline, i.e. increase the decision-maker’s costs compared to
 282 simply ignoring the forecast and using historical climatology.

283 4 Results

284 4.1 Ranked Probability Skill Score

285 Tab. 2 presents the top three performing configurations of the CP-based logistic regression model based
 286 on the combined ($RPSS_{t,v}$) for both training and validation periods. The table also includes the RPSS
 287 for the training ($RPSS_t$, 1981-2016) and validation ($RPSS_v$, 2017-2023) periods, along with the number
 288 of CPs used. Benchmark results for WARCOF and the TP variable from SEAS5 are also shown. The
 289 WS925-based model, using 13 CPs, outperformed the other configurations with an $RPSS_{t,v}$ of 0.233. It
 290 showed a good training performance ($RPSS_t = 0.218$) and reasonable validation skill ($RPSS_v = 0.310$).
 291 The WARCOF and SEAS5 TP benchmarks performed worse, with $RPSS_{t,v}$ values of 0.070 and 0.039,
 292 respectively. These three solutions are further discussed and evaluated in the subsequent sections of this
 293 results section. It should be noted here that the WARCOF period is from 1998-2023, while the SEAS5
 294 period is from 1981-2023, and thus they are not directly comparable.

Table 2: Top three performing configurations of the CP-based logistic regression according to $RPSS_{t,v}$. The table shows RPSS values for the training, validation, and combined periods, along with the count of CPs for each configuration. The benchmarks WARCOF and TP from SEAS5 are also included. *Note that the WARCOF period is from 1998-2023, while the SEAS5 period is from 1981-2023, and thus they are not directly comparable.

Configuration	CP Count	$RPSS_t$	$RPSS_v$	$RPSS_{t,v}$
WS925	13	0.218	0.310	0.233
V925	11	0.212	0.298	0.226
V10	12	0.226	0.212	0.223
WARCOF*	-	0.051	0.122	0.070
TP	-	0.051	-0.022	0.039

295 4.2 Multicategory Reliability Diagram

296 The performance of the probabilistic seasonal rainfall forecasts is further evaluated using a MCRD which
297 is presented on the left-hand side of each row, with the corresponding checkerboard plots on the right-
298 hand side (Fig. 5). Each row represents the performance of one forecasting model: WARCOF model (top
299 row, 1998–2023), SEAS5 TP dynamical model (middle row, 1981–2023), and CP-based logistic regression
300 model (bottom row, 1981–2023).

301 The WARCOF forecasts exhibit good calibration at lower quantiles (below 0.20), where the predicted
302 probabilities align closely with the observed frequencies. However, there is notable under-prediction
303 between quantiles 0.20 and 0.90 (dry bias). This may be because forecasters often assign a higher
304 probability to near-normal conditions to minimize the risk of incorrectly predicting one of the other two
305 categories. This is also shown by Mason and Chidzambwa (2008); Bliefernicht et al. (2019) and Pirret
306 et al. (2020). At higher quantiles (above 0.90), the forecasts again align well with observed frequencies.
307 Overall, the calibration is low, with relatively narrow 95% confidence intervals in the lower and upper
308 quantiles, though they widen slightly in the middle quantile range. The benchmark model exhibits a
309 relatively broad spread of errors, particularly in the mid-quantiles (e.g., 0.30 to 0.70). A significant
310 portion of forecasts remain near zero error (dark regions), though light shading at the top and bottom
311 of the plot indicates that WARCOF sometimes predicts two categories away from the observed values,
312 particularly for extreme quantiles. The average category error for WARCOF is 0.86 (95% CI: [0.79,
313 0.92]).

314 The SEAS5 TP model exhibits the best overall calibration, with a slight over-prediction in the lower
315 quantiles (0.10 to 0.40) and under-prediction in the higher quantiles (above 0.60). The 95% confidence
316 intervals are narrower than those for WARCOF, particularly in the mid-range quantiles, suggesting higher
317 certainty. This may be attributed to the larger sample size, which provides more reliable estimates across
318 the forecast distribution. SEAS5 TP shows slightly better performance in terms of categorical error
319 compared to WARCOF. There is a larger concentration of darker shading near zero error, particularly
320 in the mid-quantiles, indicating more frequent correct predictions in these ranges or just an error of
321 one category. However, in the low and high quantiles, there is some spread, with errors of one or two
322 categories being more frequent. The average category error for SEAS5 TP is 0.83 (95% CI: [0.74, 0.91]),
323 representing a modest improvement over WARCOF.

324 The CP-based logistic regression model shows good calibration, particularly in the lower quantiles
325 (up to 0.40), with slight over-prediction beyond this point. The confidence intervals are the narrowest
326 of the three models, especially for mid-range quantiles (0.40 to 0.70). The CP-based logistic regression
327 model shows the best performance in the category error, with the darkest regions concentrated around
328 zero category error, especially in the mid-quantiles (0.20 to 0.60), where this model consistently performs
329 well. Errors of two categories are rare, particularly in the mid-quantiles. The average category error for
330 this model is the lowest, at 0.72 (95% CI: [0.63, 0.82]), indicating fewer category mismatches than the
331 other models.

332 All three models show generally moderate to good calibration, with the SEAS5 TP model performing
333 the best overall, followed by CP-based logistic regression, and then WARCOF. However, the CP-based
334 model consistently provides more accurate category predictions, as indicated by the lower mean category
335 error and clustered errors around zero. SEAS5 TP shows modest improvement over WARCOF which
336 suffers from slightly larger deviations from perfect calibration and more frequent category mismatches,
337 particularly in the mid-quantile range (0.20 to 0.80).

338 4.3 Value of the Forecast System

339 Fig. 6 presents a comparison of the economic values (V) for the three models across two rainfall categories:
340 below-average and above-average. V is plotted against the cost-loss ratio, representing the trade-off faced

Figure 5: Multicategory reliability diagrams for WARCOF (1998-2023), SEAS5 TP (1981-2023), and CP-based logistic regression (1981-2023). The left column shows the observed frequency vs. forecast quantiles, with perfect calibration as the diagonal dashed line and 95% confidence interval (CI) shaded. The right column displays checkerboard plots of forecast errors, where darker shades indicate more accurate predictions (zero error).

341 by decision-makers between the cost of preventive measures and the potential loss incurred if no action
342 is taken. On the vertical axis, economic value ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating perfect forecast
343 performance and 0 indicating no added value over climatology. The horizontal axis denotes the cost-loss
344 ratio (α), where lower values suggest a relatively small cost of action compared to potential loss, and
345 higher values indicate a higher relative cost.

346 Notably, V displayed for each model represent the maximum value obtained using the optimal forecast
347 threshold. This optimal threshold is determined by evaluating a range of probability thresholds from 0.1
348 to 0.9 in increments of 0.01 (similar to Bliefernicht et al. 2019). This threshold optimization allows each
349 model to be assessed under conditions most favorable for decision-making, ensuring the highest possible
350 economic value. The following sections analyzes the performance at their respective optimal thresholds
351 for each model.

352 The left panel of Fig. 6 shows the results for below-average rainfall. The CP-based logistic regression
353 model (green curve) achieves its maximum economic value at a probability threshold of 0.25, suggesting
354 that preventive measures should be taken when the forecasted probability of below-average rainfall
355 exceeds 25%. This model provides a broad range of positive economic values across the cost-loss ratio
356 spectrum, indicating its usability in various decision-making contexts. In contrast, the SEAS5 TP model
357 (orange curve) reaches its maximum economic value at a slightly higher threshold of 0.28, but its economic
358 value declines rapidly as the cost-loss ratio increases, indicating limited applicability to specific scenarios.
359 Similarly, the WARCOF model (blue curve) peaks at a threshold of 0.26, showing a narrow range of
360 utility with diminishing economic value at higher cost-loss ratios.

361 The right panel of Fig. 6 presents the results for above-average rainfall. Here, the CP-based logistic
362 regression model outperforms the other models, with a maximum economic value at a threshold of 0.53.
363 This higher threshold suggests that preventive actions are recommended only when there is greater
364 confidence in the forecast (i.e., when the probability exceeds 53%). The model demonstrates robust
365 performance, maintaining positive economic values across a wide range of cost-loss ratios, making it
366 particularly suitable for high-cost scenarios. SEAS5 TP peaks at a threshold of 0.21, but, similar to
367 its performance in the below-average category, its economic value declines sharply beyond this point,
368 indicating effectiveness only within narrowly defined conditions. WARCOF performs best at a threshold
369 of 0.36, yet exhibits a similarly narrow range of utility, especially at higher cost-loss ratios.

370 One key takeaway from this analysis is the crucial role of selecting the appropriate probability
371 threshold to maximize the economic value of each forecasting model. The CP-based logistic regression
372 model proves to be the most robust across both rainfall categories, maintaining positive economic values
373 over a wider range of cost-loss ratios due to its higher optimal thresholds. This adaptability makes it
374 suitable for various decision-making scenarios. In contrast, SEAS5 TP and WARCOF, while effective
375 under specific conditions, show rapid declines in economic value as the cost-loss ratio increases. SEAS5
376 TP shows a sharp peak in economic value when the cost of action is low but diminishes quickly beyond its
377 optimal threshold. Similarly, WARCOF offers utility primarily at lower thresholds and cost-loss ratios.

378 Furthermore, this analysis provides insights for decision-makers, where rainfall forecasts play a critical
379 role. Understanding the relationship between probability thresholds, cost-loss ratios, and economic
380 value helps optimize strategies for taking preventive action. The threshold selection process is crucial
381 in guiding when action should be taken. For instance, using the CP-based logistic regression model,
382 preventive measures are advisable if the forecasted probability of below-average rainfall exceeds 25%.
383 This threshold reflects the point at which the benefits of action outweigh the costs. Lower thresholds, such
384 as 0.25, support a more conservative approach, appropriate for risk-averse sectors like flood management
385 or critical infrastructure. Higher thresholds, like 0.53 for above-average rainfall, suggest action should
386 be taken only when there is greater confidence in the forecast, which may be more suitable for high-
387 cost industries like large-scale agriculture, where unnecessary actions are expensive. Additionally, the
388 cost-loss ratio provides another layer of decision-making support. A lower cost-loss ratio indicates that

389 taking action is relatively inexpensive compared to potential losses, encouraging more frequent responses
 390 to forecasted events. Conversely, a higher cost-loss ratio suggests that preventive actions are more costly,
 391 necessitating selective decisions that rely on higher forecast confidence levels.

392 This section highlights the value of optimizing probability thresholds in rainfall forecasting models
 393 to maximize their economic usage. While the CP-based logistic regression model demonstrates robust
 394 performance across various scenarios, SEAS5 TP and WARCOF have more limited applications. These
 395 findings underscore the importance of context-specific decision-making in sectors reliant on accurate
 396 rainfall forecasting.

Figure 6: Economic value V as a function of the cost-loss ratio is shown for two rainfall categories below-average and above-average using the CP-based logistic regression, SEAS5 TP, and WARCOF at the threshold maximizing VV . The left panels correspond to "below-average" rainfall, while the right panels correspond to "above-average" rainfall.

397 4.4 Summary of Performance Results

398 To provide an overview of each performance, we compared key evaluation metrics across the three
 399 prediction models (WARCOF, SEAS5 TP, and CP-based logistic regression) in Tab. 3 as a summary
 400 of RPSS, calibration, category error, and economic value (V_{max}) for below-average and above-average
 401 rainfall conditions. The CP-based logistic regression model demonstrated the highest RPSS, suggesting
 402 superior predictive accuracy over the other models. SEAS5 TP showed the best calibration overall, with
 403 a lower category error compared to WARCOF, but higher than the CP-based logistic regression model.
 404 In economic value analysis, the CP-based logistic regression model provided substantial advantages
 405 under conditions of below- and above-average rainfall, highlighting its effectiveness for decision-making
 406 applications.

407 4.5 The CP-based Logistic Regression Model

408 Given the necessity of not only achieving strong forecast evaluation scores but also ensuring a model's
 409 reliability and meaningfulness in terms of statistical downscaling, it is crucial to establish a robust

Table 3: Comparison of the three seasonal rainfall prediction models (WARCOF, SEAS5 TP, and CP-based logistic regression) across key performance metrics: Ranked Probability Skill Score (RPSS), calibration quality, category error, and maximum economic value (V_{max}) for below-average and above-average rainfall scenarios.

Model	RPSS	Calibration	Category Error	V_{max}	
				Below Average	Above Average
WARCOF	0.070	moderate	0.86	0.15	0.15
SEAS5 TP	0.039	best	0.83	0.34	0.25
CP-based Log. Regr.	0.233	good	0.72	0.58	0.65

410 connection between large-scale atmospheric patterns and the target variable, in this case, the rainfall
411 categories derived through the logistic regression model. Therefore, Fig. 7 shows the composites of the
412 spatial CPs derived from WS925 anomalies (the best model, Tab. 2), which signify changes in wind
413 speed in the lower troposphere, around an altitude of 700 to 800 meters. These changes are often
414 associated with variations in the upper-air wind patterns. The monsoon winds at 925 hPa are generally
415 southwesterly during the monsoon season (approximately June to September) (see Fig. 1.19 from Fink
416 et al. 2016), bringing moisture-laden air from the Gulf of Guinea into the interior of West Africa (Lélé
417 et al., 2015). This low-level flow is a key component of the monsoon system and is strongly correlated
418 with rainfall (Janicot and Sultan, 2001; Thorncroft et al., 2011).

419 This relationship is also reflected in our analysis of CPs. Specifically, CPs exhibiting strong positive
420 anomalies in the region from 0° to 15°N , where southwesterly winds typically occur, are associated with
421 wetter-than-average conditions ($WI > 1$)¹, as seen in CP11 and CP12. This suggests an increase in
422 wind speeds, which in turn enhances the southwesterly flow. Conversely, CPs characterized by strong
423 negative anomalies in this region, such as CP6 and CP9, are associated with drier-than-average conditions
424 ($WI < 1$). This indicates a decrease in wind speeds, leading to a slowdown of the southwesterlies. The
425 association between these wind patterns and rainfall outcomes may explain these CPs as reasonable
426 predictors for categorizing rainfall as below or above average in the context of seasonal forecasting.

427 The findings from the logistic regression model further support this hypothesis (Fig. 8). The purpose
428 of these coefficients is to measure the likelihood of each CP occurring under specific categories, thereby
429 providing a foundation for understanding their sensitivity in terms of seasonal rainfall forecasting. For
430 CP11 and CP12, the coefficients are positive during wet years (0.15 and 0.20, respectively) but negative
431 during dry years (-0.15 for CP12), aligning with the observed occurrence of these CPs. This suggests
432 that these patterns play a role in enhancing rainfall when they indicate an increase in the southwesterly
433 flow. In contrast, for CP6 and CP9, the model indicates positive coefficients during dry years (0.23 for
434 CP6 and 0.11 for CP9) and negative coefficients during wet years (-0.20 for CP6 and -0.15 for CP9). This
435 behavior underscores their role in the suppression of rainfall, indicating how reduced wind speeds in these
436 patterns correlate with drier conditions. CP4 and CP8 present more neutral roles, with CP4 showing a
437 slightly positive coefficient in wet years (0.06) and negative in dry years (-0.19), while CP8 has relatively
438 small coefficients in both categories (-0.10 for dry and 0.07 for wet). This suggests a context-dependent
439 influence, potentially modulated by other atmospheric factors not directly captured in this model.

440 These results underline the importance of incorporating atmospheric dynamics into the statistical
441 downscaling process. The associations between near-surface wind patterns, and rainfall outcomes validate
442 the use of the logistic regression model, emphasizing its ability to capture the physical mechanisms
443 underlying rainfall variability in the region. This insight enhances the predictive capability of the model,
444 making it not only statistically reliable but also meaningful in a meteorological context.

¹Wetness Index (WI): Ratio of CP-specified rainfall to the long-term average

Figure 7: Atmospheric CPs for the WS925 variable as the chosen solution for the CP-based logistic regression model. The color scale signifies the mean intensity of the measured variable, where red and blue shades represent positive and negative anomalies, respectively. The Wetness Index (WI) [-] is defined as the ratio of the conditional rainfall amount of a CP to the unconditional rainfall amount for the studied period.

Figure 8: Heat map of coefficients from the multi-class logistic regression model. The color coding indicates the importance of each CP for dry, normal, or wet years.

445 5 Discussion

446 This study presents an evaluation of probabilistic seasonal rainfall forecasts for the Sudan-Sahel region
447 using three models: WARCOF, SEAS5 TP, and a CP-based logistic regression model. As highlighted,
448 seasonal rainfall variability poses significant risks to agriculture and water resource management in the
449 Sudan-Sahel region, making accurate predictions critical for mitigating adverse impacts. The results from
450 this study provide valuable insights into the performance of these models, showcasing their potential for
451 improving forecast accuracy and decision-making in vulnerable sectors.

452 The CP-based logistic regression model demonstrated the best overall performance, particularly in
453 terms of category error and economic value. This model is based on WS925 anomalies, which are strongly
454 associated with southwesterly monsoon winds that influence moisture transport from the Gulf of Guinea,
455 a key atmospheric process driving rainfall variability in the region (Janicot and Sultan, 2001; Thorncroft
456 et al., 2011; Lélé et al., 2015). By integrating these physically meaningful predictors, the CP-based
457 logistic regression model captures essential large-scale CPs, allowing it to provide more accurate and
458 reliable rainfall forecasts. This aligns with the aim to develop models that improve forecast reliability
459 through the integration of robust atmospheric processes.

460 The calibration evaluation with the MCRD analysis further underscores the usability of all three
461 forecasting products for seasonal rainfall forecasting. However, the lower average category error and
462 stronger performance in the economic value analysis of the CP-based logistic regression model indicate
463 that it provides more accurate predictions than the other models. This improvement in category error
464 aligns with the goals mentioned in previous studies (e.g., Pirret et al. 2020), which stressed the need
465 for enhancing the sharpness and reliability of seasonal forecasts in West Africa. The economic value
466 analysis reveals that the CP-based model maintains a broader range of positive economic value across
467 different cost-loss ratios, making it adaptable to a variety of decision-making contexts. This adaptability
468 is crucial for sectors dependent on rainfall, where the ability to tailor forecasts to different risk thresholds
469 can reduce economic losses.

470 One key aspect affecting model performance is the difference in temporal coverage between the
471 models. The CP-based logistic regression model and SEAS5 TP cover the period 1981–2023, whereas
472 WARCOF covers the shorter period of 1998–2023. This difference in dataset length makes direct com-
473 parisons between these models more challenging, as the longer time period likely contributes to the
474 narrower confidence intervals in SEAS5 TP and the CP-based model, given that a larger sample size
475 typically enhances forecast reliability. Nevertheless, this study builds upon and extends previous anal-
476 yses of WARCOF, incorporating additional evaluation tools such as the MCRD for recent time periods
477 (Mason and Chidzambwa, 2008; Bliefernicht et al., 2019; Pirret et al., 2020). The detection of a dry bias
478 in WARCOF is consistent with prior studies and may also be attributed to forecasters’ risk aversion and
479 biases toward near-normal conditions.

480 Despite the strengths of the CP-based logistic regression model, it is important to acknowledge
481 certain limitations. One key limitation is the model’s wet bias, which may reduce its ability to accurately
482 predict droughts and lead to an overestimation of wetter-than-average years. Given the vulnerability of
483 the Sudan-Sahel region to both drought and excess rainfall, a bias toward wet conditions could negatively
484 impact drought management strategies. This bias might reduce the model’s effectiveness for sectors like
485 agriculture, where underestimating dry conditions could result in insufficient preparation for crop failures
486 or water shortages. Addressing this wet bias is crucial for building resilience in the region (Mertz et al.,
487 2012; Wilhite et al., 2007).

488 To mitigate the wet bias and further improve the model’s accuracy, additional predictors could be
489 incorporated. For instance, integrating sea surface temperatures (Fontaine and Bigot, 1993; Losada et al.,
490 2010) or higher-level wind fields, such as the 200 hPa wind fields as an indicator of the tropical easterly jet
491 (Nicholson and Klotter, 2021) and the 700 hPa wind fields as indicators of African easterly waves or the

492 African easterly jet (Bliefernicht et al., 2022), could enhance the model’s ability to forecast both extremes
493 of rainfall variability. These additional predictors would likely improve the model’s representation of
494 atmospheric processes that drive both drought and excessive rainfall in the region, thereby reducing
495 prediction errors.

496 While the CP-based logistic regression model shows promise, further research is needed to test its
497 applicability in other regions, such as the Sahel or Guinea zones. Expanding the model to different
498 geographic contexts would allow for a better understanding of how effective it is in regions with different
499 climatic drivers. Moreover, this statistical downscaling approach could benefit from the application
500 of more advanced techniques like deep learning, which have shown potential in capturing non-linear
501 relationships between atmospheric predictors and rainfall variability (Pan et al., 2022; Patil et al., 2023;
502 Dotse, 2024). For instance, Glawion et al. (2023) presents a promising spatio-temporal downscaling
503 approach using a cGAN method, which could enhance the predictive skill of seasonal rainfall forecasts.

504 However, the simplicity of statistical downscaling methods like CP classification in combination with
505 logistic regression makes them accessible and computationally efficient, particularly for operational use in
506 developing countries. These advantages should not be overlooked when considering model improvements,
507 but integrating more complex techniques may further enhance model performance and accuracy.

508 6 Conclusion

509 This study advances seasonal rainfall prediction for West Africa by applying the statistical downscaling
510 method developed by Rauch et al. (2024), using a logistic regression model based on atmospheric CPs.
511 Building on the findings of Mason and Chidzambwa (2008), Bliefernicht et al. (2019), and Pirret et al.
512 (2020), this research offers an updated assessment of WARCOF and SEAS5 from ECMWF, providing
513 new insights into the strengths and limitations of these models in predicting rainfall variability in the
514 Sudan-Sahel region.

515 The results demonstrate that, while each of the models evaluated (WARCOF, SEAS5 TP, and
516 the CP-based logistic regression model) has distinct strengths, the CP-based model shows the greatest
517 potential for interannual rainfall prediction. This novel approach effectively links southwesterly monsoon
518 winds to rainfall variability, providing a robust statistical downscaling framework that captures the key
519 physical mechanisms driving precipitation variability in the region.

520 Calibration analysis based on a multicategory reliability diagram (Hamill, 1997) revealed that al-
521 though all models perform moderately well, the SEAS5 TP model showed the best overall calibration,
522 followed by the CP-based model and then WARCOF. However, each model suffers from biases: WAR-
523 COF demonstrates a dry bias, SEAS5 TP exhibits both dry and wet biases, and the CP-based model
524 also has also a wet bias. Notably, the CP-based model consistently delivers more accurate category
525 predictions, with lower mean category errors and tighter error distributions around zero. This makes it
526 a more robust option compared to WARCOF, which exhibits larger deviations from perfect calibration,
527 especially in the mid-quantile range. The economic value analysis further supports the potential of the
528 CP-based model, particularly across a broader range of cost-loss ratios and optimal thresholds. While
529 SEAS5 TP and WARCOF may be suitable for more narrowly defined decision-making contexts, the CP-
530 based model offers greater versatility, providing decision-makers with a more reliable tool for balancing
531 cost and risk.

532 In conclusion, this study lays a strong foundation for further enhancing seasonal forecasting in West
533 Africa. The improved accuracy and economic value demonstrated by the CP-based logistic regression
534 model highlight its potential as a reliable forecasting tool, capable of supporting more informed and
535 impactful decision-making. As forecasting tools continue to evolve, the development of adaptable, region-
536 specific models will be key to improving resilience against climate variability in the region.

537 **Funding information**

538 The author(s) declare financial support was received for the research, authorship, and/or publication
539 of this article. This study is part of the FURIFLOOD (Current and future risks of urban and rural
540 flooding in West Africa) project, which was funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research
541 in Germany (grant number: 01LG2086D).

542 **Acknowledgments**

543 We would like to thank our partners involved in the FURIFLOOD project for their invaluable support
544 over the past three years.

545 **Data Availability Statement**

546 The WARCOF data is provided by the Prévisions Climatiques Saisonnières en Afrique Soudano-Sahélienne
547 (PRESASS), organized by the African Centre of Meteorological Application for Development (ACMAD)
548 and the Centre Regional de Formation et d'Application en Agrométéorologie et Hydrologie Opérationnelle
549 (AGRYMET).

550 The rainfall data is sourced from the Climate Hazards Group Infrared Precipitation with Sta-
551 tions (CHIRPS) product (Funk et al., 2015), available for download at [https://data.chc.ucsb.edu/
552 products/CHIRPS-2.0/](https://data.chc.ucsb.edu/products/CHIRPS-2.0/).

553 The global seasonal forecast data is obtained from the SEAS5 by the European Centre for Medium-
554 Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) (Johnson et al., 2019), accessible through the Copernicus Climate
555 Data Store at <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>.

References

- ACMAD. Regional Climate Outlook Forum for Sudano-Sahelian Region (Presass 9), Last Accessed: Oct. 15, 2024, 2022. URL <https://acmad.org/index.php/regional-climate-outlook-forum-for-sudano-sahelian-regionpresass-9/>.
- J. Bliedernicht, M. Waongo, S. Salack, J. Seidel, P. Laux, and H. Kunstmann. Quality and Value of Seasonal Precipitation Forecasts Issued by the West African Regional Climate Outlook Forum. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 58(3):621–642, 3 2019. ISSN 1558-8424. doi:10.1175/JAMC-D-18-0066.1. URL <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/apme/58/3/jamc-d-18-0066.1.xml>.
- J. Bliedernicht, M. Rauch, P. Laux, and H. Kunstmann. Atmospheric circulation patterns that trigger heavy rainfall in West Africa. *International Journal of Climatology*, 42(12):6515–6536, 10 2022. ISSN 0899-8418. doi:10.1002/joc.7613. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/joc.7613>.
- H. M. Christensen, I. M. Moroz, and T. N. Palmer. Evaluation of ensemble forecast uncertainty using a new proper score: Application to medium-range and seasonal forecasts. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 141(687):538–549, 1 2015. ISSN 0035-9009. doi:10.1002/qj.2375. URL <https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.2375>.
- S. M. Coly, M. Zorom, B. Leye, A. Guiro, and H. Karambiri. Assessing climate change vulnerability and livelihood strategies in Burkina Faso including insecurity paradigm: a focus on rain-fed agriculture households. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 10 2024. ISSN 1573-2975. doi:10.1007/s10668-024-05442-3. URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10668-024-05442-3>.
- M. Dembélé and S. J. Zwart. Evaluation and comparison of satellite-based rainfall products in Burkina Faso, West Africa. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 37(17):3995–4014, 9 2016. ISSN 13665901. doi:10.1080/01431161.2016.1207258. URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01431161.2016.1207258>.
- L. Descroix, F. Guichard, M. Grippa, L. Lambert, G. Panthou, G. Mahé, L. Gal, C. Dardel, G. Quantin, L. Kergoat, Y. Bouaïta, P. Hiernaux, T. Vischel, T. Pellarin, B. Faty, C. Wilcox, M. Malam Abdou, I. Mamadou, J.-P. Vandervaere, A. Diongue-Niang, O. Ndiaye, Y. Sané, H. Dacosta, M. Gosset, C. Cassé, B. Sultan, A. Barry, O. Amogu, B. Nka Nnomo, A. Barry, and J.-E. Paturel. Evolution of Surface Hydrology in the Sahelo-Sudanian Strip: An Updated Review. *Water*, 10(6):748, 6 2018. ISSN 2073-4441. doi:10.3390/w10060748. URL <http://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/10/6/748>.
- S.-Q. Dotse. Deep learning-based long short-term memory recurrent neural networks for monthly rainfall forecasting in Ghana, West Africa. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 155(4):3033–3045, 4 2024. ISSN 0177-798X. doi:10.1007/s00704-023-04773-x. URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00704-023-04773-x>.
- A. H. Fink, T. Engel, V. Ermert, R. Van Der Linden, M. Schneidewind, R. Redl, E. Afiesimama, W. M. Thiaw, C. Yorke, M. Evans, and S. Janicot. Mean Climate and Seasonal Cycle. *Meteorology of Tropical West Africa: The Forecasters' Handbook*, pages 1–39, 1 2016. doi:10.1002/9781118391297.CH1.
- B. Fontaine and S. Bigot. West African rainfall deficits and sea surface temperatures. *International Journal of Climatology*, 13(3):271–285, 4 1993. ISSN 0899-8418. doi:10.1002/joc.3370130304. URL <https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/joc.3370130304>.

- 598 C. Funk, P. Peterson, M. Landsfeld, D. Pedreros, J. Verdin, S. Shukla, G. Husak, J. Rowland, L. Har-
599 rison, A. Hoell, and J. Michaelsen. The climate hazards infrared precipitation with stations—a new
600 environmental record for monitoring extremes. *Scientific Data* 2015 2:1, 2(1):1–21, 12 2015. ISSN
601 2052-4463. doi:10.1038/sdata.2015.66. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201566>.
- 602 L. Glawion, J. Polz, H. Kunstmann, B. Fersch, and C. Chwala. spateGAN: Spatio-Temporal Down-
603 scaling of Rainfall Fields Using a cGAN Approach. *Earth and Space Science*, 10(10), 10 2023. ISSN
604 2333-5084. doi:10.1029/2023EA002906. URL [https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/](https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2023EA002906)
605 [10.1029/2023EA002906](https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2023EA002906).
- 606 A. K. Guèye, S. Janicot, A. Niang, S. Sawadogo, B. Sultan, A. Diongue-Niang, and S. Thiria. Weather
607 regimes over Senegal during the summer monsoon season using self-organizing maps and hierar-
608 chical ascendant classification. Part I: synoptic time scale. *Climate Dynamics*, 36(1-2):1–18, 1
609 2011. ISSN 0930-7575. doi:10.1007/s00382-010-0782-6. URL [http://link.springer.com/10.1007/](http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00382-010-0782-6)
610 [s00382-010-0782-6](http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00382-010-0782-6).
- 611 A. K. Guèye, S. Janicot, A. Niang, S. Sawadogo, B. Sultan, A. Diongue-Niang, and S. Thiria. Weather
612 regimes over Senegal during the summer monsoon season using self-organizing maps and hierarchical
613 ascendant classification. Part II: Interannual time scale. *Climate Dynamics*, 39(9-10):2251–2272, 11
614 2012. ISSN 09307575. doi:10.1007/S00382-012-1346-8.
- 615 S. M. Hagos and K. H. Cook. Ocean Warming and Late-Twentieth-Century Sahel Drought and Recovery.
616 *Journal of Climate*, 21(15):3797–3814, 8 2008. ISSN 0894-8755. doi:10.1175/2008JCLI2055.1. URL
617 <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/clim/21/15/2008jcli2055.1.xml>.
- 618 T. M. Hamill. Reliability Diagrams for Multicategory Probabilistic Forecasts. *Weather and Forecasting*,
619 12(4):736–741, 12 1997. ISSN 0882-8156. doi:10.1175/1520-0434(1997)012<0736:RDFMPF>2.0.CO;2.
620 URL [http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/1520-0434\(1997\)012%3C0736:RDFMPF%3E2.0.](http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/1520-0434(1997)012%3C0736:RDFMPF%3E2.0.CO;2)
621 [CO;2](http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/1520-0434(1997)012%3C0736:RDFMPF%3E2.0.CO;2).
- 622 Z. Hao, V. P. Singh, and Y. Xia. Seasonal Drought Prediction: Advances, Challenges, and Future
623 Prospects. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 56(1):108–141, 3 2018. ISSN 8755-1209. doi:10.1002/2016RG000549.
624 URL <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/2016RG000549>.
- 625 M. C. M. HOUNGIBO, B. MINOUNGOU, S. B. TRAORE, R. I. MAIDMENT, A. ALHASSANE, and A. ALI. Validation
626 of high-resolution satellite precipitation products over West Africa for rainfall monitoring and early
627 warning. *Frontiers in Climate*, 5, 7 2023. ISSN 2624-9553. doi:10.3389/fclim.2023.1185754. URL
628 <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fclim.2023.1185754/full>.
- 629 S. Janicot and B. Sultan. Intra-seasonal modulation of convection in the West African Monsoon. *Geo-*
630 *physical Research Letters*, 28(3):523–526, 2 2001. ISSN 0094-8276. doi:10.1029/2000GL012424. URL
631 <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2000GL012424>.
- 632 S. J. Johnson, T. N. Stockdale, L. Ferranti, M. A. Balmaseda, F. Molteni, L. Magnusson, S. Tietsche,
633 D. Decremmer, A. Weisheimer, G. Balsamo, S. P. E. Keeley, K. Mogensen, H. Zuo, and B. M. Monge-
634 Sanz. SEAS5: the new ECMWF seasonal forecast system. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(3):
635 1087–1117, 3 2019. ISSN 1991-9603. doi:10.5194/gmd-12-1087-2019. URL [https://gmd.copernicus.](https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/12/1087/2019/)
636 [org/articles/12/1087/2019/](https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/12/1087/2019/).
- 637 C. Klein, D. Heinzeller, J. Bliefernicht, and H. Kunstmann. Variability of West African monsoon
638 patterns generated by a WRF multi-physics ensemble. *Climate Dynamics*, 45(9-10):2733–2755, 11
639 2015. ISSN 0930-7575. doi:10.1007/s00382-015-2505-5. URL [http://link.springer.com/10.1007/](http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00382-015-2505-5)
640 [s00382-015-2505-5](http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00382-015-2505-5).

- 641 C. Kouakou, J. E. Paturel, F. Satgé, Y. Tramblay, D. Defrance, and N. Rouché. Comparison of gridded
642 precipitation estimates for regional hydrological modeling in West and Central Africa. *Journal of*
643 *Hydrology: Regional Studies*, 47:101409, 6 2023. ISSN 2214-5818. doi:10.1016/J.EJRH.2023.101409.
- 644 A. Kumar, A. G. Barnston, and M. P. Hoerling. Seasonal Predictions, Probabilistic Verifica-
645 tions, and Ensemble Size. *Journal of Climate*, 14(7):1671–1676, 4 2001. ISSN 0894-8755.
646 doi:10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014<1671:SPPVAE>2.0.CO;2. URL [http://journals.ametsoc.org/
647 doi/10.1175/1520-0442\(2001\)014%3C1671:SPPVAE%3E2.0.CO;2](http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014%3C1671:SPPVAE%3E2.0.CO;2).
- 648 M. I. Lélé, L. M. Leslie, and P. J. Lamb. Analysis of Low-Level Atmospheric Moisture Transport
649 Associated with the West African Monsoon. *Journal of Climate*, 28(11):4414–4430, 6 2015. ISSN
650 0894-8755. doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00746.1. URL [http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/
651 JCLI-D-14-00746.1](http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00746.1).
- 652 M. Lorenz, J. Bliedernicht, B. Haese, and H. Kunstmann. Copula-based downscaling of daily precipitation
653 fields. *Hydrological Processes*, 32(23):3479–3494, 11 2018. ISSN 1099-1085. doi:10.1002/HYP.13271.
- 654 T. Losada, B. Rodríguez-Fonseca, S. Janicot, S. Gervois, F. Chauvin, and P. Ruti. A multi-model
655 approach to the Atlantic Equatorial mode: impact on the West African monsoon. *Climate Dynamics*,
656 35(1):29–43, 7 2010. ISSN 0930-7575. doi:10.1007/s00382-009-0625-5. URL [http://link.springer.
657 com/10.1007/s00382-009-0625-5](http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00382-009-0625-5).
- 658 R. Manzanás. Assessing the suitability of statistical downscaling approaches for seasonal forecasting in
659 Senegal. *Atmospheric Science Letters*, 18(9):381–386, 9 2017. ISSN 1530-261X. doi:10.1002/asl.767.
660 URL <https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/asl.767>.
- 661 S. Mason and S. Chidzambwa. Position Paper: Verification of African RCOF Forecasts. *Technical Report*
662 *#09-02*, RCOF Revie, 2008. doi:<https://doi.org/10.7916/D85T3SB0>.
- 663 O. Mertz, S. D’haen, A. Maiga, I. B. Moussa, B. Barbier, A. Diouf, D. Diallo, E. D. Da, and D. Dabi.
664 Climate Variability and Environmental Stress in the Sudan-Sahel Zone of West Africa. *AMBIO*, 41
665 (4):380–392, 6 2012. ISSN 0044-7447. doi:10.1007/s13280-011-0231-8. URL [http://link.springer.
666 com/10.1007/s13280-011-0231-8](http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s13280-011-0231-8).
- 667 V. Moron, A. W. Robertson, M. N. Ward, and O. Ndiaye. Weather Types and Rainfall over Sene-
668 gal. Part I: Observational Analysis. *Journal of Climate*, 21(2):266–287, 1 2008. ISSN 1520-0442.
669 doi:10.1175/2007JCLI1601.1. URL <http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/2007JCLI1601.1>.
- 670 O. Ndiaye, M. N. Ward, and W. M. Thiaw. Predictability of Seasonal Sahel Rainfall Using GCMs and
671 Lead-Time Improvements Through the Use of a Coupled Model. *Journal of Climate*, 24(7):1931–1949,
672 4 2011. ISSN 0894-8755. doi:10.1175/2010JCLI3557.1. URL [http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/
673 10.1175/2010JCLI3557.1](http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/2010JCLI3557.1).
- 674 S. E. Nicholson and D. Klotter. The Tropical Easterly Jet over Africa, its representation in six reanalysis
675 products, and its association with Sahel rainfall. *International Journal of Climatology*, 41(1):328–347,
676 1 2021. ISSN 1097-0088. doi:10.1002/JOC.6623. URL [https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/
677 full/10.1002/joc.6623](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/joc.6623).
- 678 Z. Nouaceur and O. Murarescu. Rainfall Variability and Trend Analysis of Rainfall in West Africa (Sene-
679 gal, Mauritania, Burkina Faso). *Water*, 12(6):1754, 6 2020. ISSN 2073-4441. doi:10.3390/w12061754.
680 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/12/6/1754>.

- 681 H. Paeth, A. H. Fink, S. Pohle, F. Keis, H. Mächel, and C. Samimi. Meteorological characteristics and
682 potential causes of the 2007 flood in sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Climatology*, 31(13):
683 1908–1926, 11 2011. ISSN 08998418. doi:10.1002/joc.2199. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/joc.2199>.
- 685 H. Paeth, A. Paxian, D. V. Sein, D. Jacob, H.-J. Panitz, M. Warscher, A. H. Fink, H. Kunstmann, M. Breil, T. Engel, A. Krause, J. Toedter, and B. Ahrens. Decadal and multi-year
686 predictability of the West African monsoon and the role of dynamical downscaling. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, 26(4):363–377, 10 2017. ISSN 0941-2948. doi:10.1127/metz/2017/0811.
687 URL http://www.schweizerbart.de/papers/metz/detail/26/87336/Decadal_and_multi_year_predictability_of_the_West_af=crossref.
- 691 B. Pan, G. J. Anderson, A. Goncalves, D. D. Lucas, C. J. W. Bonfils, and J. Lee. Improving Seasonal
692 Forecast Using Probabilistic Deep Learning. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 14(3), 3
693 2022. ISSN 1942-2466. doi:10.1029/2021MS002766. URL <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2021MS002766>.
- 695 K. R. Patil, T. Doi, and S. K. Behera. Predicting extreme floods and droughts in East Africa using a
696 deep learning approach. *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science*, 6(1):108, 8 2023. ISSN 2397-3722.
697 doi:10.1038/s41612-023-00435-x. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41612-023-00435-x>.
- 698 J. S. R. Pirret, J. D. Daron, P. E. Bett, N. Fournier, and A. K. Foamouhoue. Assessing the Skill
699 and Reliability of Seasonal Climate Forecasts in Sahelian West Africa. *Weather and Forecasting*, 35
700 (3):1035–1050, 6 2020. ISSN 0882-8156. doi:10.1175/WAF-D-19-0168.1. URL <https://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/WAF-D-19-0168.1>.
- 702 A. Polasky, J. L. Evans, and J. D. Fuentes. Statistical downscaling for precipitation pro-
703 jections in West Africa. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 155(1):327–347, 1 2024.
704 ISSN 0177-798X. doi:10.1007/s00704-023-04637-4. URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00704-023-04637-4>.
- 706 T. C. Portele, C. Lorenz, B. Dibrani, P. Laux, J. Bliefernicht, and H. Kunstmann. Seasonal forecasts
707 offer economic benefit for hydrological decision making in semi-arid regions. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1):
708 10581, 5 2021. ISSN 2045-2322. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-89564-y. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-89564-y>.
- 710 M. Rauch, J. Bliefernicht, P. Laux, S. Salack, M. Waongo, and H. Kunstmann. Seasonal Forecasting
711 of the Onset of the Rainy Season in West Africa. *Atmosphere 2019, Vol. 10, Page 528*, 10(9):528, 9
712 2019. ISSN 20734433. doi:10.3390/ATMOS10090528.
- 713 M. Rauch, J. Bliefernicht, and H. Kunstmann. Interannual Rainfall Variability in West
714 Africa: Reconstruction based on Atmospheric Circulation Patterns. *Zenodo*, Preprint, 2024.
715 doi:10.5281/zenodo.14046485.
- 716 D. S. Richardson. Skill and relative economic value of the ECMWF ensemble prediction system.
717 *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 126(563):649–667, 1 2000. ISSN 0035-
718 9009. doi:10.1002/qj.49712656313. URL <https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.49712656313>.
- 720 D. S. Richardson. Economic Value and Skill. In *Forecast Verification*, pages 167–184. Wiley, 12
721 2011. doi:10.1002/9781119960003.ch9. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/9781119960003.ch9>.
- 722

- 723 F. Semazzi. Framework for climate services in developing countries. *Climate Research*, 47(1):145–150,
724 3 2011. ISSN 0936-577X. doi:10.3354/cr00955. URL [http://www.int-res.com/abstracts/cr/v47/
725 n1-2/p145-150/](http://www.int-res.com/abstracts/cr/v47/n1-2/p145-150/).
- 726 E. K. Siabi, A. T. Kabobah, K. Akpoti, G. K. Anornu, M. Amo-Boateng, and E. K. Nyantakyi. Statistical
727 downscaling of global circulation models to assess future climate changes in the Black Volta basin of
728 Ghana. *Environmental Challenges*, 5:100299, 12 2021. ISSN 26670100. doi:10.1016/j.envc.2021.100299.
729 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2667010021002754>.
- 730 J. Siegmund, J. Bliefernicht, P. Laux, and H. Kunstmann. Toward a seasonal precipitation pre-
731 diction system for West Africa: Performance of CFSv2 and high-resolution dynamical downscal-
732 ing. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 120(15):7316–7339, 8 2015. ISSN 2169-
733 897X. doi:10.1002/2014JD022692. URL [https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.
734 1002/2014JD022692](https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/2014JD022692).
- 735 C. D. Thorncroft, H. Nguyen, C. Zhang, and P. Peyrill. Annual cycle of the West African monsoon:
736 regional circulations and associated water vapour transport. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Me-
737 teorological Society*, 137(654):129–147, 1 2011. ISSN 00359009. doi:10.1002/qj.728. URL [https:
738 //onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.728](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.728).
- 739 A. P. Weigel, M. A. Liniger, and C. Appenzeller. The Discrete Brier and Ranked Probability Skill Scores.
740 *Monthly Weather Review*, 135(1):118–124, 1 2007. ISSN 1520-0493. doi:10.1175/MWR3280.1. URL
741 <http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/MWR3280.1>.
- 742 D. A. Wilhite, M. D. Svoboda, and M. J. Hayes. Understanding the complex impacts of drought: A key
743 to enhancing drought mitigation and preparedness. *Water Resources Management*, 21(5):763–774, 5
744 2007. ISSN 0920-4741. doi:10.1007/s11269-006-9076-5. URL [https://link.springer.com/10.1007/
745 s11269-006-9076-5](https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11269-006-9076-5).
- 746 D. Wilks. *Statistical Methods in the Atmospheric Sciences*. Elsevier, second edi edition, 2006. ISBN
747 978-0-12-751966-1.
- 748 D. S. Wilks. A skill score based on economic value for probability forecasts. *Meteorological Ap-
749 plications*, 8(2):209–219, 6 2001. ISSN 1350-4827. doi:10.1017/S1350482701002092. URL [https:
750 //rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1017/S1350482701002092](https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1017/S1350482701002092).
- 751 G. Yengoh. Climate and Food Production: Understanding Vulnerability from Past Trends in Africa’s
752 Sudan-Sahel. *Sustainability*, 5(1):52–71, 12 2012. ISSN 2071-1050. doi:10.3390/su5010052. URL
753 <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/5/1/52>.
- 754 N. Zampaligr, L. H. Dossa, and E. Schlecht. Climate change and variability: perception and adapta-
755 tion strategies of pastoralists and agro-pastoralists across different zones of Burkina Faso. *Regional
756 Environmental Change*, 14(2):769–783, 4 2014. ISSN 1436-3798. doi:10.1007/s10113-013-0532-5. URL
757 <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10113-013-0532-5>.

Figure S1: WARCOF forecast map for the July-August-September season, 2018.

**Les prévisions des quantités totales des précipitations
pour la période de Juillet à Septembre**

Figure S2: WARCOF forecast map for the July-August-September season, 2019.

**PREVISION SAISONNIERE DES PRECIPITATIONS
 POUR LA REGION SOUDANO-SAHELIENNE
 VALABLE POUR JUILLET-AOUT-SEPTEMBRE 2020
 ELABOREE LE 24 AVRIL 2020**

Figure S3: WARCOF forecast map for the July-August-September season, 2020.

Figure S4: WARCOF forecast map for the July-August-September season, 2021.

Figure S5: WARCOF forecast map for the July-August-September season, 2022.

Figure S6: WARCOF forecast map for the July-August-September season, 2023.

Figure S7: WARCOF forecast map for the July-August-September season, 2024.

Table S1: WARCOF probabilities for the target area (Fig. 2) - Distribution of years by below average, near average, and above average categories.

Year	Below average	Near average	Above average
1998	0.30	0.40	0.30
1999	0.20	0.40	0.40
2000	0.20	0.45	0.35
2001	0.25	0.45	0.30
2002	0.30	0.45	0.25
2003	0.20	0.50	0.30
2004	0.30	0.40	0.30
2005	0.20	0.40	0.40
2006	0.30	0.35	0.35
2007	0.20	0.40	0.40
2008	0.15	0.35	0.50
2009	0.35	0.40	0.25
2010	0.15	0.45	0.40
2011	0.20	0.45	0.35
2012	0.15	0.40	0.45
2013	0.20	0.40	0.40
2014	0.35	0.45	0.20
2015	0.33	0.33	0.33
2016	0.20	0.40	0.40
2017	0.20	0.35	0.45
2018	0.20	0.35	0.45
2019	0.20	0.35	0.45
2020	0.20	0.30	0.50
2021	0.20	0.35	0.45
2022	0.20	0.45	0.35
2023	0.20	0.35	0.45

Table S2: SEAS5 probabilities for the target area (Fig. 2) - Distribution of years by below average, near average, and above average categories.

Year	Below average	Near average	Above average
1981	0.44	0.20	0.36
1982	0.64	0.32	0.04
1983	0.92	0.04	0.04
1984	0.40	0.32	0.28
1985	0.32	0.44	0.24
1986	0.44	0.32	0.24
1987	0.72	0.20	0.08
1988	0.24	0.40	0.36
1989	0.24	0.36	0.40
1990	0.28	0.56	0.16
1991	0.56	0.24	0.20
1992	0.92	0.08	0.00
1993	0.68	0.24	0.08
1994	0.48	0.24	0.28
1995	0.36	0.40	0.24
1996	0.32	0.44	0.24
1997	0.48	0.32	0.20
1998	0.40	0.32	0.28
1999	0.00	0.16	0.84
2000	0.12	0.32	0.56
2001	0.04	0.32	0.64
2002	0.16	0.32	0.52
2003	0.16	0.28	0.56
2004	0.28	0.40	0.32
2005	0.16	0.64	0.20
2006	0.16	0.20	0.64
2007	0.00	0.40	0.60
2008	0.04	0.24	0.72
2009	0.36	0.40	0.24
2010	0.20	0.28	0.52
2011	0.16	0.44	0.40
2012	0.24	0.28	0.48
2013	0.16	0.48	0.36
2014	0.24	0.44	0.32
2015	0.48	0.28	0.24
2016	0.56	0.20	0.24
2017	0.35	0.31	0.33
2018	0.25	0.33	0.41
2019	0.31	0.49	0.20
2020	0.39	0.31	0.29
2021	0.27	0.29	0.43
2022	0.16	0.43	0.41
2023	0.33	0.29	0.37
2024	0.33	0.33	0.33

Figure S8: Reliability diagrams for the CP-based logistic regression model (1981-2023). The diagrams illustrate the reliability across three event categories: above-average, near-average, and below-average. The top row shows the observed frequency against forecast probability, with the ideal reliability represented by the diagonal dashed line. The 95% confidence intervals, assessed through bootstrapping, are depicted as error bars around the predicted frequencies (x-axis). The bottom row displays the forecast occurrence distribution for each category.

Figure S9: Reliability diagrams for the SEAS5 TP predictions (1981-2023). Same as Fig. S8.

Figure S10: Reliability diagrams for the WARCOF predictions (1998-2023). Same as Fig. S8.